

Dirac Equation in Cosmological Inertial Frame

Sangwha-Yi*

Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

*Corresponding Author: Sangwha-Yi, Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

Abstract: Dirac equation is a one order-wave equation. Wave function uses as a probability amplitude in quantum mechanics. We make Dirac Equation from wave function, Type A in cosmological inertial frame. The Dirac equation satisfy Klein-Gordon equation in cosmological inertial frame.

Keywords: Gordon Equation; Cosmological Inertial Frame; Dirac equation;

PACS Number: 03.30.+p, 03.65

1. INTRODUCTION

Dirac equation is in special relativity theory, [8]

$$(i\hbar\gamma^\mu\partial_\mu - mcI)\psi = 0 \quad ,$$

I is 4×4 unit matrix ,

$$\gamma^0 = \begin{pmatrix} I' & 0 \\ 0 & -I' \end{pmatrix}, \quad \gamma^i = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma^i \\ -\sigma^i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

I' is 2×2 unit matrix, σ^i is Pauli's matrix. (1)

2. DIRAC EQUATION FROM WAVE FUNCTION-TYPE A IN COSMOLOGICAL INERTIAL FRAME

Dirac equation is the wave equation. Therefore, Dirac equation is in cosmological inertial frame, [2]

Wave function Type A:

$$r \rightarrow r\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)} \quad , \quad t \rightarrow \frac{t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} \quad ,$$

t_0 is the cosmological time. $\Omega(t_0)$ is the expanding ratio of universe in the cosmological time t_0 .

$$(i\hbar\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}\gamma^0\partial_0 + i\hbar\frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}\gamma^i\partial_i - mcI)\phi = 0 \quad (2)$$

If $\bar{\partial}_\mu$ is

$$\bar{\partial}_\mu = (\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}\partial_0, \frac{1}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}\partial_i) \quad (3)$$

Dirac equation is in cosmological inertial frame,

$$(i\hbar\gamma^\mu\bar{\partial}_\mu - mcI)\phi = 0 \quad (4)$$

Eq(4) multiply $i\hbar\gamma^\nu\bar{\partial}_\nu$, hence

$$(-\hbar^2(\gamma^\mu \bar{\partial}_\mu)(\gamma^\nu \bar{\partial}_\nu) - i\hbar(\gamma^\nu \bar{\partial}_\nu)mcI)\phi = 0 \quad (5)$$

In this time,

$$i\hbar\gamma^\nu \bar{\partial}_\nu \phi = mcI\phi \quad (6)$$

Hence, Eq(5) is

$$(-\hbar^2\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu \bar{\partial}_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu - m^2c^2I)\phi = 0 \quad (7)$$

In this time, matrix γ^μ is

$$\frac{1}{2}(\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu) = \frac{1}{2}\{\gamma^\mu, \gamma^\nu\} = \eta^{\mu\nu}I \quad (8)$$

Therefore,[1],[3]

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2}(\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu)\bar{\partial}_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu \phi + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2}I\phi \\ &= (\eta^{\mu\nu}\bar{\partial}_\mu \bar{\partial}_\nu + \frac{m^2c^2}{\hbar^2})I\phi = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Eq(9) is the matrix equation of Klein-Gordon.

Dirac spinor ϕ is $\phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4)$. ϕ 's hermitian conjugate $\phi^+ = (\phi_1^*, \phi_2^*, \phi_3^*, \phi_4^*)$.

Hence, ϕ 's adjoint spinor $\bar{\phi}$ is

$$\bar{\phi} = \phi^+ \gamma^0, \quad \bar{\phi}(i\gamma^\mu \bar{\partial}_\mu + mcI) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Hence, positive probability density j^0 is

$$j^0 = \bar{\phi}\gamma^0\phi = \phi^+\phi = |\phi_1|^2 + |\phi_2|^2 + |\phi_3|^2 + |\phi_4|^2 \quad (11)$$

3. CONCLUSION

We found Dirac equation from Wave Function-Type A in cosmological special theory of relativity. The wave function uses as a probability amplitude.

REFERENCES

- [1]S.Yi, "Klein-Gordon Equation and Wave Function in Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science, **7**,12(2020),pp4-6
- [2]S.Yi, "Yukawa Potential in Klein-Gordon Equation in Cosmological Inertial Frame", International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science, **8**,3(2021),pp16-18
- [3]S.Yi, "Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity" International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science, **7**,11(2020),pp4-9

- [4]A.Beiser,"Concepts of Modern Physics"4th Edition,(Mcgraw-Hill,1994)
- [5]J.D. Bjorken & S. D. Drell, Relativistic Quantum Field(McGraw- Hill Co., 1965)
- [6]P.Bergman,Introduction to the Theory of Relativity(Dover Pub. Co.,Inc., New York,1976),Chapter V
- [7]R.L.Liboff, Quantum Mechanics(Addison-Wesley Publishing Co., Inc.,1990)
- [8]A.Beiser, Concept of Modern Physics(McGraw-Hill,Inc.,1991)

Citation: Sangwha-Yi (2021) Dirac Equation in Cosmological Inertial Frame. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science (IJARPS)* 8(7), pp.4-6, 2021.

Copyright: © 2021 Authors, This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.